

Originalni naučni rad

NEW POSSIBILITIES FOR THE APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN EDUCATION

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Abstract

In this research paper, the concept of artificial intelligence, advantages and disadvantages, and new possibilities of applying methods, techniques, and tools of artificial intelligence in the function of improving the educational process will be explored and presented. Based on the review of the latest academic discourse in this field, the possibilities of the ChatGPT tool will be presented, and the way it can help teachers and students in mastering the teaching content. The fundamental goal of this research is the evaluation of new possibilities of applying artificial intelligence and ChatGPT in the creation of appropriate teaching content. The methodology of a combination of qualitative and quantitative methods of scientific research will be applied in the paper. For the purposes of the paper, research will be conducted in educational institutions of primary and secondary education in Kosovo and Metohija with the aim of showing the effects of practical application and indicators of adoption or acceptance by teachers and students. The results of research and experience from practice, especially after the pandemic caused by the COVID 19 virus, show that teachers who have mastered digital competencies and skills use ChatGPT more productively in order to improve their teaching potential in creating original teaching materials, e.g. didactic games, thus enabling inclusion, easier and faster adaptation of teaching to the individual needs of each student.

Keywords: Artificial intelligence, ChatGPT, electronic teaching

NOVE MOGUĆNOSTI PRIMENE VEŠTAČKE INTELEGENCIJE U OBRAZOVANJU

Apstrakt

U ovom istraživačkom radu biće istražen i predstavljen koncept veštačke inteligencije, prednosti i mane i nove mogućnosti primene metoda, tehnika i alata veštačke inteligencije u funkciji unapređenja obrazovnog procesa. Na osnovu pregleda najnovije literature u ovoj oblasti, biće predstavljene mogućnosti alata ChatGPT i način na koji on može pomoći nastavnicima i učenicima u savladavanju nastavnih sadržaja. Osnovni cilj rada je evaluacija novih mogućnosti primene veštačke inteligencije i ChatGPT-a, u kreiranju odgovarajućeg nastavnog sadržaja. U radu će biti primenjena metodologija kombinacije kvalitativnih i kvantitativnih metoda naučnog istraživanja. Za potrebe rada, istraživanje će biti sprovedeno u obrazovnim ustanovama osnovnog i srednjeg obrazovanja na Kosovu i Metohiji sa ciljem da se prikažu efekti praktične primene i indikatori usvajanja ili prihvatanja od strane nastavnika i učenika. Rezultati istraživanja i iskustva iz prakse, posebno nakon pandemije izazvane virusom COVID-19, pokazuju da nastavnici koji su savladali digitalne kompetencije i veštine produktivnije koriste ChatGPT kako bi unapredili svoj nastavni potencijal u kreiranju originalnih nastavnih materijala, npr. didaktičkih igara, čime omogućavaju inkluziju, lakše i brže prilagođavanje nastave individualnim potrebama svakog učenika.

ključne reči: Veštačka inteligencija, ChatGPT, elektronska nastava

INTRODUCTION

Artificial intelligence is a broad field of computer science that deals with the development of systems capable of performing tasks that typically require human intelligence. The development of artificial intelligence dates back to the middle of the 20th century, when Alan Turing and John McCarthy began to explore the possibilities of creating intelligent machines - we call this period the birth of artificial intelligence. Artificial intelligence has progressed the most especially since 2005, because it has become more and more present in our everyday life, from speech recognition to smart homes and cars (Mehan, 2022). The integration of artificial intelligence into the world of education brings significant changes, as it introduces new methods of learning and teaching (Walter, 2024). Well-known authors describe artificial intelligence as computer systems capable of performing human processes, such as learning, adaptation, and automatic correction (Crompton & Burke, 2023). Some authors state that artificial intelligence combines knowledge from social sciences, computer science, and systemic neuroscience (Mehan, 2022). Artificial intelligence has also achieved significant success in the fields of robotics, healthcare, finance, economics, as well as in the fields of speech and face recognition. In this context, it is stated in the literature that the fields of artificial intelligence are expanding to many other disciplines (Vinay, 2023).

THEORETICAL BACKGROUND OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE

The existing research emphasizes that artificial intelligence is a key technological advance that enables the replacement of manual work with intellectual work, as it can perform various tasks. In this respect, it can be said that it is not a single technology, but includes several areas, such as machine learning and deep learning, which add intelligence to applications with different approaches. Based on this, it can be concluded that methods such as supervised learning, where labeled data are used to learn models, and unsupervised learning, where patterns are sought in unlabeled data, represent the basis for the development of artificial intelligence. Artificial intelligence, among other things, allows organizations to use large amounts of data generated by customers and gain valuable insights and analytics in order to adjust marketing strategies and personalize the user experience (Denić, 2024). Research by well-known authors Kaplan and Haenlein says that technological progress is replacing physical labor in jobs that require more cognitive abilities. One of the goals of artificial intelligence is for computers to understand and simulate human advanced cognition, which would enable them to recognize emotions and understand human feelings. The field of artificial intelligence is still very under-researched and, as such, full of questions and challenges. Its under exploration and complexity presents interesting topics for deeper research and understanding of the depth of artificial intelligence (Emmert-Streib et al., 2020). Many companies are researching and analyzing the possibilities of applying this technology, and its versatility is confirmed by the fact that it is already being used in various sectors. On the other hand, there is a significant lack of theoretical knowledge, which is why companies, despite the implementation of this technology, still do not achieve the expected results.

APPLICATION OF ARTIFICIAL INTELLIGENCE IN EDUCATION

In the world of education, the appropriate integration of artificial intelligence can bring significant positive changes, as it can introduce new methods of learning and teaching. Results in practice show that the inclusion of artificial intelligence in education goes beyond technological progress, as it fundamentally reshapes the educational experience (Walter, 2024). Some authors state that artificial intelligence can simulate personal teaching, support collaborative learning, guide students through didactic games, virtual environments, and enable personalized assessment and feedback, which gives teachers a deeper insight into the individual student (Zavacki-Richter et al., 2019). In the last decade, researchers have increasingly recognized the positive effects and potential of artificial intelligence in education and have explored the use of artificial intelligence to support learning, especially through intelligent tutors and adaptive educational systems (Crompton & Burke, 2023). However, ensuring quality education also requires caution, as artificial intelligence must take into account complex social, pedagogical, and environmental factors (Xu & Ouyang, 2022). Advances in artificial intelligence over the years also enable customized assessment and feedback, giving teachers deeper insight into individual

students (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). One of the models or tools of artificial intelligence that is increasingly applied in education is ChatGPT (Chat Generative Pre-trained Transformer). The results show that the application of artificial intelligence, i.e., ChatGPT, can increase the effectiveness of learning by adapting experiences to the needs of individual students. ChatGPT is an artificial intelligence model that has the ability to provide individualized answers to questions that can lead to fraud, such as rewriting homework and helping with knowledge tests (Lo, 2023). In this regard, ChatGPT is known for its speed and efficiency in communication, enabling the rapid exchange of text-based messages. It functions as an intelligent personal assistant that operates continuously and uses natural language processing (NLP) to create a personalized experience for each user. ChatGPT was first introduced in 2020 and operates on a large database that includes various types of sources, from books to websites (Bringula, 2023). In this sense, students can ask questions about the material, solve problems, or get additional explanations using chatbots that use ChatGPT technology. It provides interactive learning and support outside the classroom, allowing students to access information and resources whenever they need them. Also, Chat GPT can simulate a conversation with historical figures or virtual characters to enhance learning through simulations and practice. In addition to the above, artificial intelligence enables digitally adapted learning, as it can suggest educational materials that are aligned with the individual's learning style (Pardamean et al., 2022). However, despite the evident benefits, research shows that a high percentage of students do not approve of the complete replacement of human teachers with artificial intelligence (Ryu & Han, 2018). This is followed by the opinions of the authors who point out that technology is only an assistant, which cannot replace human interpersonal relationships and the traditional way of teaching (Vinay, 2023). The advantages of using a chatbot are numerous, and some of them are: 1) availability of information at the moment the user needs it, 2) sending personalized offers and notifications, and 3) collecting feedback from users. Pupils and students who might have difficulty following in a regular classroom environment can now use the ability of artificial intelligence to tailor content and delivery to their specific needs, thereby removing barriers to learning and fostering a more inclusive educational environment (Walter, 2024). Chat GPT uses deep learning and neural networks for language processing. After being trained on a huge amount of data, the model acquires the ability to understand context, semantics, and grammar, which allows it to generate meaningful and relevant answers to the questions or statements posed. Research in practice shows that ChatGPT is already being used in education, helping teachers and students prepare teaching materials, solve complex problems, or learn programming (Rahman & Watanobe, 2023). In our environment, the Belgrade Academy of Business and Art Vocational Studies, in order to save time, better and faster communication with students, was among the first to implement an ADA chat bot (Academic Digital Assistant) in order to provide services and information to students 24 hours a day, 7 days a week. Some authors report that ChatGPT has proven to be a useful tool for developing students' writing skills, as through interaction with it, they can receive spelling corrections, suggestions for improvements, and detailed feedback on their writing, which allows them to improve

their writing technical skills (Montenegro-Rueda et al., 2023). In this context, for teachers, ChatGPT improves insight into students' needs through data analysis, which allows teachers to better focus on different learning strategies and innovations in curriculum design (Hasanein & Sobaih, 2023). Teachers can use it to prepare content, such as lesson plans, presentations, quizzes, assessments, and writing research papers (Ngo, 2023). The results show that with proper use, users can use the full potential of ChatGPT in their work, which leads to better results (White et al., 2023)

RESEARCH METHODOLOGY

This research work is based on many years of scientific research work and theoretical knowledge, acquired during studies, studying domestic and, above all, foreign academic discourse, as well as on practical experiences of studying and monitoring the implementation of artificial intelligence in education. Research methods are based on description, analysis, and observation, the method of compilation, presentation, and assessment of the theoretical and practical aspects of the analysis of the application of artificial intelligence in educational practice. Essentially, the methodology of the combination of qualitative and quantitative methods of scientific research will be applied in the work.

RESEARCH RESULTS

The importance of applying new technologies in all areas is exceptional, this is confirmed by a study by the company Intercom, where it is stated that "business leaders saved an average of 300,000 US dollars in 2019 from their chat bots, and the biggest impact was on support and sales teams" (source: Marketing Land). The application of artificial intelligence, specifically ChatGPT, in education can provide faster access to information, be an additional support in the work of formal teaching, especially in environments where physical assistance is not possible, then a high level of interactivity, and systematization of specific problems and practical or seminar papers. Educational games not only connect different parts of the learning process but also make the learning process more fun and efficient (Korei et al., 2021). Research results show that it is essential to integrate educational games into the educational process in a way that increases learning effectiveness, student activity, and strengthens their initiative and creativity (Gorard et al., 2016).

DISCUSSION OF RESULTS

Artificial intelligence, with its ability to process large amounts of data and automate tasks, significantly increases efficiency and accuracy in many areas (Denić, 2024). By providing different opinions to improve the way of expression, it can help students develop their writing skills and encourage a more tolerant attitude towards their own work (Bringula, 2023). It is especially useful in education to provide timely support

to children with special needs, thereby enriching their learning and everyday life (Walter, 2024). Success depends on the learner, not the AI, because learners must actively manage their learning with little support from the teacher (Hwang, 2022). The use of chatbots for the promotion and individual support of students reduces repetitive tasks and improves the processes of receiving and distributing financial and other resources (Pisica et al., 2023). ChatGPT helps teachers reduce curriculum overload by using fast and accurate information. In this context, artificial intelligence has various advantages that require the integration of technologies and human work, thereby improving operational efficiency and increasing business value (Goodwin & Quiroz Vazquez, 2024). Some authors state that ChatGPT, created by the organization OpenAI (Bringula, 2023), provides various opportunities for experiential learning, where students actively participate, reflect on the acquired knowledge, and connect new ideas with their existing knowledge (Cacicio & Riggs, 2023). In that sense, unlike humans, a chatbot is designed for multitasking and can handle thousands of user queries at the same time. Recent research indicates that ChatGPT has shown exceptional potential in supporting students with special needs by providing specialized tools and resources that are tailored to different learning challenges (Walter, 2024). In addition to the above benefits, the great thing about chatbots is that they can be integrated into existing messaging applications that people already use for everyday communication, such as Facebook Messenger, Viber, and others, which brings brands closer to customers (Cao, 2022)

In connection with artificial intelligence, there are no guarantees for the protection of personal data, and there may also be student fraud when using certain programs and chatbots, which additionally opens up ethical issues (Pisica et al., 2023). In the weaknesses of artificial intelligence, the well-known author Grewal (2021) notes that the negative aspects of artificial intelligence mainly include a lack of trust, which can negatively affect the quality of relationships between actors. Education through artificial intelligence requires an emphasis on creativity and technological proficiency to encourage innovation and critical thinking. This requires a change in the way of thinking about education in the age of artificial intelligence, from classical methods to more dynamic, interactive, and student-focused teaching environments (Walter, 2024). Also, artificial intelligence can create inaccurate or even false information and develop the skill of avoiding plagiarism detectors, which calls into question the authenticity and uniqueness of student works (Bringula, 2023). Stojanović J (2024) states that the use of artificial intelligence for organizations also involves high implementation costs. The disadvantages are manifested in the absence of responsibility of algorithms, chatbots, and robots. There is also no guarantee for the protection of personal data, and student fraud may occur when using certain programs and chat rooms, which raises questions of ethical principles (Pisica et al., 2023). There are also questions related to the reliability and transparency of AI-generated responses. Critics warn that dependence on a single source of information could lead to a lack of objectivity and diversity of perspectives, as well as the risk of spreading inaccurate or incomplete data.

For the effective application of artificial intelligence in education, the development of digital literacy skills, engineering knowledge, and critical thinking to overcome these difficulties is crucial (Walter, 2024). In addition to the above, artificial intelligence has another important application in education, as it will also determine educational strategies based on the learning styles of individual students. In this regard, some authors predict that by 2028, the education system should be barely recognizable. Also, its application brings ethical challenges, such as data privacy and replacing human jobs with automated systems (Zawacki-Richter et al., 2019). Research results also show that the application of artificial intelligence in education focuses on its use to support teachers in designing lessons, promoting learning, students, and transforming educational systems (Xu & Ouiang, 2022). However, it should be emphasized that ChatGPT is not omnipotent, and the interpretation of what the program enables in the public is often misinterpreted.

CONCLUSION

The results of the research show that artificial intelligence cannot yet replace the human approach in the education process, and specifically in the creation of quality didactic games, because it does not know the specifics of the class or the needs of individual students. The research shows that Chat GPT is basically an advanced natural language processing technology that uses artificial intelligence to enable human-computer interaction through text. In this sense, Chat GPT can certainly help the way of learning, synthesis of knowledge, expression, and shifting the focus from the end result to the method and procedure. Chatbots can be used to provide educational resources to students, such as quizzes, exercises, and even one-on-one tutoring. In this context, the conclusion is that the application of methods, techniques and tools of artificial intelligence in education is extremely useful for getting ideas and for individualizing learning content, because it can help in adapting tasks to different levels of learning and creating more demanding content that would otherwise require much more time and effort. The new ChatGPT technology allows users to receive precise and detailed answers directly from artificial intelligence instead of traditional search results, which represents a major change in the way of using the Internet. From the relevant scholarly work, the conclusion can be drawn that despite the increasing use of artificial intelligence in the teaching process in various forms and the creation of teaching materials and didactic games, it is still insufficiently used, and that this tool could be used more effectively. As artificial intelligence and machine learning technology continue to develop, it is likely that chat bots will become even more sophisticated and used in even more diverse applications. The results of the research show that for the application of artificial intelligence in education to be effective, educators must be well-educated, i.e., digitally literate, to create and create a working environment for learning in which teaching materials and games become both fun and learning. Predictions show that in the future, it may be difficult to distinguish between a conversation with a chatbot and a live agent. Chatbots will play an increasing role in providing customer support and automating

tasks in all industries. In this sense, the teaching materials, i.e., the didactic games themselves, should be adapted to the individual needs and interests of the students, and in addition, at the same time, it is mandatory to keep the emphasis on the achievement of the teaching goals.

REFERENCES

1. Bringula, R. (2023) What do academics have to say about ChatGPT? A text mining analytics on the discussions regarding ChatGPT on research writing. *AI Ethics*, 1–13. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s43681-023-00354-w>
2. Cacicio, S. in Riggs, R. (2023). ChatGPT: Leveraging AI to Support Personalized Teaching and Learning. *Adult Literacy Education*, 70. <http://doi.org/10.35847/SCacicio.RRiggs.5.2.70>
3. Crompton, H. in Burke, D. (2023). Artificial intelligence in higher education: the state of the field. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 20(1), 22. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-023-00392-8>
4. Denić, N., Milić, M., Stojanović, K., Stojanović, J. and Milić, A. (2024). „Digital literacy as a key factor in successful education“. *6th International Conference on Applied Engineering and Natural Sciences September 25-26, 2024. Konya, Turkey.*
5. Denić, N., Stojanović, K., Stojanović, J., Milić, M., and Obradović, D., Educational software of modern trends in development and application *6th International Conference on Applied Engineering and Natural Sciences, September 25-26, 2024 : Konya, Turkey,*
6. Emmert-Streib, F., Yli-Harja, O. in Dehmer, M. (2020). Artificial intelligence: A clarification of misconceptions, myths and desired status. *Frontiers in artificial intelligence*, 3, 524339. <https://doi.org/10.3389/frai.2020.524339>
7. Goodwin, M., & Quiroz Vazquez, C. (2024, September 20). *IBM*. Retrieved from What is artificial intelligence (AI) in business?: <https://www.ibm.com/topics/artificial-intelligence-business>
8. Gorard, S., See, B. H. in Morris, R. (2016). Teacher Review of effective teaching approaches in primary schools. Durham University, Department for Education. <https://durham-repository.worktribe.com/output/1636290>
9. Grewal, D., Guha, A., Satornino, C. B., & Schweiger, E. B. (2021). Artificial intelligence: The light and the darkness. *Journal of Business Research*, 136, 229–236.
10. Hasanein, A. M. in Sobaih, A. E. E. (2023). Drivers and Consequences of ChatGPT Use in Higher Education: Key Stakeholder Perspectives. *European Journal of Investigation in Health, Psychology and Education*, 13(11), 2599–2614. <https://doi.org/10.3390/ejihpe13110181>
11. Hwang, S. (2022). Examining the Effects of Artificial Intelligence on Elementary Students' Mathematics Achievement: A Meta-Analysis. *Sustainability*, 14(20), 13185. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su142013185>
12. Julie Mehan. (2022). Artificial Intelligence: Ethical, Social, and Security Impacts for the Present and the Future. IT Governance Publishing. <http://digital.casalini.it/9781787783713>
13. Körei, A., Szilágyi, S. in Török, Z. (2021). Integrating didactic games in higher education: Benefits and challenges. *Teaching Mathematics and Computer Science*, 19(1), 1–15. <https://doi.org/10.5485/TMCS.2021.0517>

14. Pardamean, B., Suparyanto, T., Cenggoro, T. W., Sudigyo, D. in Anugrahana, A. (2022). AI-based learning style prediction in online learning for primary education. *IEEE Access*, 10, 35725–35735. <https://doi.org/10.1109/ACCESS.2022.3160177>
15. Pisica, A. I., Edu, T., Zaharia, R. M. in Zaharia, R. (2023). Implementing artificial intelligence in higher education: Pros and cons from the perspectives of academics. *Societies*, 13(5), 118. <https://doi.org/10.3390/soc13050118>
16. Stojanović, J., Stojanović, K., Denić, N., & Milić, M. (2024). Application of artificial intelligence in education in the function of raising entrepreneurial competence. *SCIENCE International Journal*, 3(3), 149–152. <https://doi.org/10.35120/sciencej0303149s>
17. Stojanović, J., Petkovic, D., M Alarifi, I., Cao, Y., Denic, N., Ilic, J., Assilzadeh, H., Resic, S., Petkovic, B., Khan, A., Milickovic, M., „Application of distance learning in mathematics through adaptive neuro-fuzzy learning method“, *Computers and Electrical Engineering*, 2021, 107270, DOI: 10.1016/j.compeleceng.2021.107270
18. Y. Cao, Z. M. AlKubaisy, J. Stojanović, J., Denić, N., Petković, D., Zlatković, D., and Zakić, A. „Appraisal of information and communications technologies on the teaching process by neuro fuzzy logic“. 2022, *Comput. Appl. Eng. Educ.*, 1–24. <https://doi.org/10.1002/cae.22486>
19. Vinay, S. B. (2023). Application of Artificial Intelligence (AI) In School Teaching and Learning Process-Review and Analysis. *Information Technology and Management*, 14(1), 1-5. <https://doi.org/10.17605/OSF.IO/AERNV>
20. Walter, Y. (2024). Embracing the future of Artificial Intelligence in the classroom: the relevance of AI literacy, prompt engineering, and critical thinking in modern education. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 21(1), 15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-024-00448-3>
21. Xu, W. in Ouyang, F. (2022). The application of AI technologies in STEM education: a systematic review from 2011 to 2021. *International Journal of STEM Education*, 9(1), 59. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40594-022-00377-5>
22. Zawacki-Richter, O., Marín, V. I., Bond, M. in Gouverneur, F. (2019). Systematic review of research on artificial intelligence applications in higher education—where are the educators?. *International Journal of Educational Technology in Higher Education*, 16(1), 1–27. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s41239-019-0171-0>

REZIME

U ovom istraživačkom radu biće detaljno analiziran i predstavljen koncept veštačke inteligencije (VI), njene prednosti i nedostaci, kao i nove mogućnosti primene savremenih metoda, tehnika i alata zasnovanih na VI u cilju unapređenja obrazovnog procesa. Poseban fokus stavljen je na praktičnu upotrebu alata ChatGPT, jednog od najpoznatijih modela generativne veštačke inteligencije, i način na koji može doprineti podršci učenju i nastavi kroz personalizaciju sadržaja, automatizaciju određenih nastavnih aktivnosti i osnaživanje nastavnika u njihovoj svakodnevnoj praksi. Na osnovu savremene stručne i naučne literature, istražuju se konkretni primeri primene ChatGPT-a u različitim obrazovnim kontekstima, pri čemu se procenjuju mogućnosti za njegovu integraciju u nastavni plan i program, kreiranje originalnih didaktičkih materijala, evaluaciju znanja i razvoj kritičkog mišljenja kod učenika. Osnovni cilj rada

jeste evaluacija potencijala veštačke inteligencije i alata poput ChatGPT-a u kreiranju efikasnog, fleksibilnog i inkluzivnog obrazovnog okruženja. U metodološkom delu, rad se oslanja na kombinaciju kvalitativnih i kvantitativnih istraživačkih pristupa. Istraživanje će biti sprovedeno u osnovnim i srednjim školama na prostoru Kosova i Metohije, sa ciljem analize stepena prihvatanja i konkretne primene VI alata od strane nastavnika i učenika. Poseban značaj ima analiza iskustava nakon pandemije izazvane virusom COVID-19, kada je digitalna transformacija obrazovanja postala neizbežna, a potreba za razvojem digitalnih kompetencija dobila na značaju. Rezultati istraživanja ukazuju na to da nastavnici koji su uspešno usvojili digitalne veštine koriste ChatGPT ne samo kao tehnički alat, već i kao sredstvo za kreativnu i inkluzivnu nastavu – putem izrade interaktivnih zadataka, didaktičkih igara, scenarija za nastavu i materijala koji omogućavaju prilagođavanje individualnim potrebama učenika. U tom kontekstu, veštačka inteligencija se prepoznaje kao potencijalni nosilac transformacije obrazovanja, ali istovremeno se otvaraju pitanja etike, odgovorne upotrebe i neophodnosti kontinuiranog stručnog usavršavanja obrazovnog kadra.